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A STUDY ON IMPACT OF CROSS CULTURAL DIFFERENCES AFFECTING BUSINESS ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract:

In the business world, communication is imperative for the successful execution of daily operations and smooth functioning of the business. Understanding of cultural differences and overcoming language barriers are some of the considerations people should have when dealing with business with people of various cultures. Often business deals are lost because the parties involved did not take the time to learn about their each others' cultures prior to interacting. So for a successful management, any person should be able to work with people from different cultural backgrounds no matter what their cultural orientation they have in order to be the best. The current study is an attempt to highlight the various cultural differences and how they affect business organizations in present Scenario.

Keywords: *Cultural, Management and Barriers.*

Introduction:

Culture in general is concerned with beliefs and values on the basis of which people interpret experiences and behave, individually and in groups. Broadly and simply put, "culture" refers to a group or community with which you share common experiences that shape the way you understand the world. Culture is learned, shared, and transmitted from one generation to the next.

Culture can be passed from parents to children, by social organizations, special interest groups, the government, schools, and churches. Culture is multidimensional, consisting of a number of common elements that are interdependent.

Cross cultural communication has become strategically important to companies due to the growth of global business, technology and the Internet. Understanding cross-cultural communication is important for any company that has a diverse workforce or plans on conducting global business. This type of communication involves an understanding of how people from different cultures speak, communicate and perceive the world around them.

Cross-cultural communication in an organization deals with understanding different business customs, beliefs and communication strategies. Language differences, high-context vs. low-context cultures, nonverbal differences and power distance are major factors that can affect cross-cultural communication.

From the above picture it can be well understood that this symbol in USA means OK, In Japan means Money, In Russia it means Zero and in Brazil it is considered as an Insult.

Review of Literature:

According to Nancy Adler (2008), she gives a good definition of cross cultural management: “Cross-cultural management explains the behavior of people in organizations around the world and shows people how to work in organizations with employees and client populations from many different cultures.” The importance of cross-cultural management lies in the on-growing co-operation between companies in different countries where difficulties may arise because of the different cultural backgrounds. One of the well-known researchers in the field of culture and management is Geert Hofstede (1980).

Therefore, Hofstede’s work is considered indispensable to any study on culture and management. He developed what is called a “dimensional approach to cross-cultural comparisons.” As the world is witnessing nowadays “globalization”, more and more companies are being run in different places all around the world. This will result in more activities all over the world which result in communication across cultures. Culture is something that human beings learn and as a result, learning requires communication and communication is a way of coding and decoding language as well as symbols used in that language.

For example, humans communicate through many means other than language such as facial expressions, gestures, body language, posture etc. In other words, culture and communication can be considered inseparable, if one is to be exposed to a certain culture, then communication becomes a must. The first to introduce the term “intercultural communication” was Edward T. Hall which he defined as “communication between two persons of different cultures”.

The term “Intercultural business communication” is a new term in the world of business which may be defined as the communication that takes place within businesses whereby there are employees from different cultural backgrounds. On the other hand, there is another term which is “International communication” which means the communication that takes place between nations and governments rather than individuals (Chaney & Martin, 2011). Therefore, good knowledge of intercultural communication as well as international business communication is of utmost importance to give individuals the opportunity to compete internationally. Cross-cultural communication is imperative for companies that have a diverse workforce and participate in the global economy. It is important for employees to understand the factors that are part of an effective, diverse workforce.

Objectives of the Study:

- To analyze about various cross –cultural differences affecting the Business Organizations.
- To highlight some of the problems which are faced by the organizations in International Market and the ways to manage such types of issues.

Importance of the Study

- The study is helpful in understanding of the different organizational cultures.
- The study is useful in knowing about the cultures barriers and how to overcome them

Cultural Barriers faced by Business Organizations:

- **Language:** A common cross cultural barrier in business communication is of course, language. Although English is regarded as the common international language of business, not every business globally uses English on a regular basis. Employees may have more difficulty when communicating in English, which can lead to misunderstandings when taking direction, understanding level of urgency and communicating issues or concerns. Never assume that because your instructions receive head nods. Check for real understanding by asking others to summarize what they just heard you say. The business world is littered with poor translations that have caused great embracement due to lack of cultural sensitivity.

The following are some of the language barriers faced in the business world. Coors had its slogan “Turn it loose, it translated into Spanish, where it became “suffer from diarrhea. The Japanese seems to have a particular flair for naming products. The country has given gems like homo soap, Germ Bread and Shinto mix.

- **Cultural Barriers:** Every culture has a different set of values, business ethics, accepted behavior and decorum– even different facial expressions and gestures. It is important to understand these differences – to show genuine respect for other cultural mores –when communicating with professionals from other cultures. For example, in the United States it is common for the speaker to share personal anecdotes to build audience report, but in other countries this is considered tiresome. Humor can be especially tricky to employ; better to be straightforward rather than run the risk that your joke may inadvertently embarrass or insult the listener. No two cultures are the same.

The American and Indian cultures have very vast differentiation between them..While the culture of America is a mixture of different cultures, the Indian culture is unique and has its own values. One of the major differences that can be seen between American and Indian culture is in family relations. While the Indians are very much family oriented, the Americans are individual oriented. In Indian culture, the family values are given more prominence than the individual values. Indians respect family values. On the other hand, in American culture the individual values get prominence than the family values. Indians are more committed to their family where as the Americans are more committed to themselves only. In another sense, it can be said that the American culture is more goal oriented and the Indian culture is more people or family oriented. Indians may even forsake their individual wishes and also happiness for the sake of families.

- **Presentation Style:** Believe it or not, culture influences how people in different countries prefer to receive information. For example, how interactive you should make your presentation depends on the culture to which you present. In general, English speaking cultures like presentations to be lively and interactive. However, Eastern Europeans are accustomed to presentations that are formal, high detailed and with few interruptions. Questions are answered either at the end of presentation.
- Japanese audiences expect more technical information. Canadians, like Americans, enjoy a brisk pace; and Latin American audiences prefer a speech with a high level of emotional appeal

Conclusion:

It can be said that culture is a wide spread phenomenon which cannot be separately identified from the group of people who share a set of accepted behaviours, customs and values. It is quite obvious that the impact of shared culture would result in decision making for business Organizations. However the following points should be considered such as:

- Proper market research of the country should be there where the business needs to be established so that the culture of the country can be understood. For Example Noodles were alright for dinner once in a while and it is accepted in other countries as well but it is quite unsuccessful in India. Since Indians consider Idly, dosa, chappathi in their dinner menu. Then Maggie changed the strategy for the Indian Market, and marketed it as a snack not as a dinner and it succeeded in the market. This also reveals how culturally bounded practices impact the marketing strategies. They came up with other flavours seeing to the Indian Market.
- It is very important to understand the language, negotiation style, way of working and body language.
- Proper knowledge of the pricing strategies to be followed is also important for Example MNC's like KFC and MC Donald's give more concern to the price which they charge from Sri Lankans since people in Sri Lanka are more conscious about the prices of product than the quality. Even the displays they use. This proves that MNCs are amending their marketing strategies regarding their prices in order to suit in the Sri Lankan Market.
- Developing of the standard operating procedures which need to be followed by all the stakeholders of the business.
- Maintaining cordial relations with the stakeholders, employees and vendors. Proper understanding of the distribution channel is also important . For examples the countries like Australia, USA and other European Countries have their own distribution channel. While in other countries lie Jordan and UAE , they male use of their native good distributor to distribute their tea since these customers buy the products which comes from their own distributors.

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